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Aligning open educational resources to new taxonomies: How AI technologies can help and in which scenarios

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ABSTRACT

Aligning open educational resources (OER) to skill taxonomies is a common task in the education field and helps teachers better locate material that aligns with the standards of their curriculum. When taxonomies change, as they periodically do, re-tagging the increasing mass of open educational resources is needed. The process of manual tagging is, however, exceedingly labor intensive. We propose and evaluate a novel combination of machine learning methods to help automate tagging open educational resources with skills from an existing taxonomy as well as skills from any newly introduced taxonomy. We collected text, image figures, and videos from tens of thousands of educational resources from two major digital learning platforms to answer the research questions of: how effective are machine learning models in automatically updating OER classification to reflect a new taxonomy (RQ1), and which models may be of practical use in different scenarios (RQ2)? Using several taxonomies, including the US Common Core, we find that while full automation is not practically viable, our most generalizable model can reach non-expert human labeling performance requiring only 100 labeled examples and near expert level with 5000. We believe these novel findings may have immediate utility for practitioners and policymakers and better ready the growing landscape of open educational resources for the advent of new taxonomies ahead. We publicly release our pre-trained US Common Core and new taxonomy tagging models, providing guidance on their viability in various real-world scenarios.

1. Introduction

States set standards and define taxonomies used to establish learning objectives and assessment criteria for their primary and secondary school systems. When these standards change, the tectonic plates of an educational system and its curricula can be slow to align. Free online learning materials, called Open Educational Resources (OER), have both increased in their abundance and in their share of teaching materials used in schools, with institutional adoption of them accelerated under remote instruction during the COVID pandemic (Huang et al., 2020; Stracke et al., 2022). When standards change, OER platforms and other education technologies too must scramble to align. This alignment is a very time-intensive, laborious process that increases in cost with the number of resources needing re-alignment. Both the number of OER platforms as well as the number of resources on each platform are expanding. For example, Learning Resource Exchange, a platform based in Europe that collects OERs and makes them searchable, started with approximately

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128,000 OERs in 2008 (Massart, 2009) and has expanded to more than 300,000 OERs in 2022 according to their website.¹ With the hundreds of OER platforms in operation, the number of OERs is likely in the tens of millions. At this scale, relying purely on manual categorization and alignment of resources is untenable and will likely have a negative impact on state policies toward releasing new standards.

In the meantime, natural language processing technologies have seen tremendous advancement in recent years and achieved high performance in many tasks (Chowdhary & Chowdhary, 2020, pp. 603–649; Khurana et al., 2022; Lauriola et al., 2022). Pre-trained large language models (LLM), such as ChatGPT (Ouyang et al., 2022), are made available to the public and have since gone viral, breaking through in popular culture. According to several recent studies (Shen et al., 2021a, 2021b; Li et al., 2021; Matsuda et al., 2022), the alignment of educational resources to taxonomies can benefit from the latest technologies too. For example, Shen et al. (2021b) utilized an LLM called task adaptive BERT to classify skill labels of problem descriptions, skill descriptions, and video titles. Leveraging the latest technologies to expedite educational resources alignment to taxonomies is meaningful in several aspects. First, as Chiu et al. (2023) pointed out, one of the major challenges in the artificial intelligence in education (AIED) field is the lack of learning resources for adaptive learning. Since many learning platforms rely on skills or knowledge components for measurement and recommendation, automatic skill labeling could increase the number of resources that are available to learning platforms for personalized recommendation. It may improve investment in adaptive learning systems as well, with investors knowing that the product's life cycle can extend beyond the window of the skill taxonomy of the day. Second, a faster alignment process could be a strong reason to urge policymakers to improve the standards more frequently. For example, the US Common Core State Standards (CCSS), a nation-wide standard in the United States, has received a lot of criticism on the standards itself since initial launch (Rebarber & McCluskey, 2018), but has not had any revisions, and many states have decided to leave the Common Core. One major reason for the stagnancy is that the alignment to new standards takes a large amount of time and resources (Lavenia et al., 2015; McLaughlin et al., 2014). With accelerated alignment, it will be easier to improve standards and re-use and re-align existing content. Practically, there is also the matter of other aspects of the educational enterprise aligning with new standards, not the least of which is the human-element, teacher uptake and matriculation into the new curricular lens. Third, automatic item tagging can also lower the barrier to entry for new OERs and new educational technologies, leading to more quality content options for educators and positively impacting learning experiences.

Therefore, in this paper, we propose a set of new automatic skill tagging models to address these issues, and pose a research question: (RQ1) how effective are machine learning models in automatically updating OER classification to reflect a new taxonomy? The introduced models utilize LLMs and multimodal data (e.g., the text and images of a problem), and can be leveraged to map OERs to newly introduced taxonomies without retraining on labels from the new taxonomy. To improve the practical implications of our work, we open source two robust pre-trained models, designed to associate math content with the US Common Core State Standards in Mathematics. We establish a baseline in the task of predicting the Common Core skills of a problem or video, and set a benchmark in the novel task of predicting the skill of a problem from a new taxonomy not seen in model training. We present results on how much data is required to achieve different practical tiers of performance, and give guidance on readiness for practical adoption and circumstances in which more research is needed. The code of the models can be found in our public repository.² Our second research question is therefore: (RQ2) which models may be of practical use in different scenarios?

2. Background

In this section, we give a brief overview of skill taxonomies used around the world by state governments and private education technology platforms. We then provide additional background on the Common Core, a taxonomy that is the focus of our empirical analyses.

2.1. Skill taxonomies

Skill taxonomies are commonly used to design standardized tests as well as educational learning platforms across the globe. They are produced at different levels of government and by private industry, and are often different from country to country, state to state, and platform to platform. For example, at the country level, the United States adopted the Common Core States Standards for K-12 English language arts and mathematics, and Next Generation Science Standards³ for K12 sciences after previously having had different standards by state. For example, Massachusetts had the Massachusetts Comprehensive Assessment System,⁴ and Minnesota had the Minnesota Comprehensive Assessments.⁵ Recently some states left the Common Core State Standards and switched back to their own standards again, for instance, New York adopted its Next Generation Learning Standards⁶ in place of Common Core. Looking outside of the United States, China maintains its National Curriculum Standards for every subject including Chinese language, mathematics,

¹ <http://www.eun.org/resources/learning-resource-exchange>.

² <https://github.com/CAHLR/skill-tagging>.

³ <https://www.nextgenscience.org/>.

⁴ <https://www.doe.mass.edu/mcas/>.

⁵ <https://www.minnstate.edu/system/asa/academicaffairs/academicreadiness/mca.html>.

⁶ <https://www.nysed.gov/next-generation-learning-standards>.

English, science, and liberal arts, among other subjects. They guide the curriculum setting in its nine-year compulsory education⁷ and secondary schools.⁸ Europe adopts the European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations standards,⁹ which categorizes and describes 13,890 skills for 3008 professional occupations in the labor market. This standard is mainly used for job seeking, education, and training purposes. Educational technology platforms developed by private industry and non-profits also develop their own taxonomies. MATHia (formerly Cognitive Tutor)¹⁰ defined a fine-grained taxonomy of over 2000 skills called “knowledge components” (Aleven & Koedinger, 2013) that are used to trace student cognitive mastery. Khan Academy,¹¹ a popular non-profit OER and tutoring platform, has its own taxonomy breaking down high-level topics into subtopics and lessons. Finally, ASSISTments,¹² an academic institution run math and science tutoring system, has several versions of its skill taxonomies used to enumerate skills in Algebra, Geometry, and other subjects (Razzaq et al., 2007). In addition to creating their own taxonomies for the purpose of aligning to the tutoring approach of their system, they often also adopt state standard taxonomies to align their content to the curricula of state educators.

Taxonomies usually change periodically. For example, Virginia has established a law to update its Standards of Learning every seven years (Code of Virginia, 2022, chap. 13.2), and Japan revises its National Curriculum Standards every ten years.¹³

2.2. Common Core State Standards

The history of the taxonomies in the United States shows the periodicity with which taxonomies change over time (Fig. 1). At the beginning of this century, the No Child Left Behind Act (Public Law, 2002) in the United States mandated that all schools administer annual standardized tests in reading and math for accountability purposes, for students in grades 3 through 8. Some states had annual standard tests before this federal legislation passed in 2001, for example, the Massachusetts Comprehensive Assessment System (MCAS) was first administered in 1993 (Esposito, 2004). Following the passage of the No Child Left Behind Act, Minnesota, for example, established the Minnesota Comprehensive Assessments-II in 2003 (Lombard, 2006). Given that each state was allowed to develop its own standards under the law, it was difficult to compare results across states. To address this issue, the Common Core State Standards were introduced in 2009 as a solution to create a common national standard (Porter et al., 2011). The Common Core initiative aspired to build consistent educational standards and evaluation systems across the states. Common Core as a standard provides learning goals for students, but not detailed curricula, leaving that to local schools and districts to design and implement (National Governors Association, 2010).

Under the Common Core, each state needed to align its own previous standards with Common Core, publish the new standards after multiple stakeholders’ feedback, and implement the new standards. To adopt and implement the new standards, states needed to invest considerable time and money. The timeline for adoption and implementation of the Common Core varied across the states but mostly had taken place over several years. For example, the California State Board of Education adopted the Common Core State Standards in 2010 but did not finish making modifications to the Math and English standards until early 2013. The teaching materials aligned with Common Core then became available to districts for the 2014–2015 school year. But a survey of California teachers from 2016 to 2018 stressed that higher-quality instructional materials aligned with the standards was still the biggest concern (Kirst, 2020). Massachusetts adopted the Common Core State Standards in 2010 as well but delayed the Common Core testing for two years in 2013 (Peterson et al., 2016) worrying that a complete switch to Common Core would be “too precipitous” for districts and schools. States also used different tools for analyzing how their state standards were aligned with the common standards. For instance, Florida and Georgia used the Achieve Common Core Comparison Tool in their analysis, and South Carolina used the Council of Chief State School Officers Survey of Enacted Curriculum tool (Anderson et al., 2012).

Since its release, 41 states have adopted the Common Core State Standards. Common Core has not been revised after the initial release, but several states (e.g., California) have made modifications after adopting them. In recent years, many states have left or are leaving the Common Core, signaling an upcoming expiration or revision. For example, New York State decided to adopt Next Generation Learning Standards in place of Common Core in 2017. The first assessments aligned to the Next Generation Learning Standards will be hosted in Spring 2023. While there are signs that a successor taxonomy may be around the corner, Common Core remains the most adopted set of mathematics standards in the nation, with 30 states still utilizing it in K-12. A survey conducted in five states (Kane et al., 2016, p. 56) found that 69% of principals think that Common Core will lead to better student learning. Another survey had similar results that more than two thirds of principals and teachers believe Common Core will have a positive impact than previous standards (WestEd, 2016). According to the California Department of Education, the rate of meeting or exceeding standards in 3rd graders have both increased around 10% in English and math from 2015 to 2019 (Kirst, 2020). While not perfect, the Common Core State Standards will likely still be the most important standards in the United States for several years to come.

⁷ https://www.moe.gov.cn/srcsite/A26/s8001/202204/t20220420_619921.html.

⁸ https://www.moe.gov.cn/srcsite/A26/s8001/202006/t20200603_462199.html.

⁹ <https://esco.ec.europa.eu/en>.

¹⁰ <https://www.carnegielearning.com/solutions/math/mathia/>.

¹¹ <https://www.khanacademy.org/>.

¹² <https://new.assistments.org/>.

¹³ https://www.us.emb-japan.go.jp/itpr_en/education-system-in-japan.html.

Fig. 1. Timeline of select taxonomies and related legislation introduced in the United States. This depicts the cadence at which taxonomies have been modified and new ones have been introduced over time.

2.3. Alignment to taxonomies

When new taxonomies are released or modifications are made to them, considerable alignment work must be done to keep the learning materials relevant to the new standards. States need to map their old standards to the new, as they did when Common Core was launched. This process of mapping is sometimes referred to as a “crosswalk” (Conley, 2011; Subramaniam et al., 2013). Teaching materials also need to be aligned with the new taxonomies as well (Crawford, 2011; Moschkovich, 2012). Digital learning platforms, too, need to make sure their content is aligned with the latest standards. For instance, Khan Academy and CK12¹⁴ have put effort into mapping their content to the Common Core State Standards (Welz, 2017).

The alignment process is never easy. And even after all the hard work, there is still a substantial amount of misalignment existing in the education system. For example, Beach (2011) identified a misalignment between state standards and the Common Core in English language arts, Polikoff (2015) found that textbooks systematically overemphasize procedures and memorization compared to what the standards suggested, Yu et al. (2022) revealed that biology curriculum standards and textbooks in China are not well aligned, and Barthakur et al. (2022) suggested the alignment between the assessments and learning objectives could be improved in a MOOC course.

When a new taxonomy is introduced, skill tagging of items can be done by either mapping old skills (and all associated items) to new skills, or mapping items to new skills individually. In the case where the old and new taxonomies are of similar granularity and quality, a skill-to-skill mapping (i.e., crosswalk) is appropriate and requires less work. However, the introduction of a new taxonomy usually comes with a different granularity and criteria for categorization. This means that two items previously tagged as a single skill in the previous taxonomy may each belong to a separate skill in the new taxonomy, necessitating item-level re-labeling.

3. Related work

While the majority of the alignment of OERs to taxonomies is done by human experts today, there has been some prior research leveraging other resources to accelerate this process. One cluster of works tried to involve non-experts, but the results were not very promising. Moore et al. (2020) explored crowdsourcing the alignment and found that 33% of the crowdsourced skills matched those generated by domain experts. And according to Moore et al. (2022), only 12% of skill tags generated by students met expert level and more than half were not usable. Ren et al. (2024) suggested that non-experts were able to identify only half of the skills labeled by experts. Another group of works investigated automated skill tagging with algorithms. Yilmazel et al. (2007) applied rule-based techniques to transfer features from skill descriptions in one standard to another standard using a machine learning classifier. Karlovčec et al. (2012) used Support Vector Machine and Nearest Neighbor on simple text processing of problem text to classify skills. Pardos & Dadu (2017) used problem text and problem sequences they call “context” to tag skills with a Nearest Neighbor classifier. Patikorn et al. (2019) explored out-of-sample platform prediction and found it much less accurate; they then reduced platform overfitting by removing HTML markup from problem text and reducing the number of duplicate problems in the training data. Li et al. (2021) utilized problem text and response sequences in modern neural networks for generating crosswalks between taxonomies. Recently, as BERT-based machine learning models (Kenton & Toutanova, 2019) became the state-of-art method in many natural language processing tasks, several papers introduced variants of the model to automated skill tagging. Shen et al. (2021b) applied a variant called “task adaptive BERT” on problem descriptions, skill descriptions, and video titles for skill classification. Matsuda et al. (2022) inferred latent skills from courseware content leveraging SentenceBERT, and Shen et al., 2021a proposed MathBERT, a BERT-based model trained on mathematics corpora.

However, past research on algorithm-based alignment has not addressed a few key issues that prevent the models from being practically viable. First, most models proposed by previous research require alignment labels for model training first. The training

¹⁴ <https://www.ck12.org/>.

labels could be too expensive or unrealistic to obtain in some cases. Additionally, with taxonomies evolving over time, the alignment labels need to be updated accordingly. We believe that zero-shot learning (Pourpanah, et al., 2022; Xian et al., 2018), the technique that allows models like ChatGPT to complete tasks not seen in training, is potentially helpful towards the ends of developing models that can align to new taxonomies without retraining. Matsuda et al. (2022)'s work does not require training labels, but their approach is to infer new labels, instead of tagging contents with expert created taxonomies, which is a different research question from ours. Second, previous studies only explored using text to predict skills, but many OERs have more than just texts (e.g., an illustrative image), and some OERs do not have texts (e.g., lecture videos). Despite the extensive studies on multimodal data and fusion techniques in the machine learning field (Sleeman IV et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2020), it has not been explored in skill tagging yet. Finally, currently there are no publicly available pre-trained models for widely used taxonomies such as the US Common Core State Standards. We believe providing such models can increase the potential impact of AI in practice. AI-human collaboration has also been evaluated for data labeling tasks. For example, Desmond et al. (2021) used an AI-assisted interface to increase both the accuracy and speed of human data labeling of customer service tickets. But according to Weisz et al. (2022), the benefits of a code generation model to software engineers could be various with different tasks and settings, which argued for the need of a well-designed user interface. It has been observed by several prior research (Chiu et al., 2023; Kaufmann, 2021) that people tend to have less trust in AI than real humans, so we should be careful when designing the user interface and manuals of AI models. In education, Yang et al. (2021) proposed the idea of human-centered artificial intelligence in education, which suggests considering human conditions and contexts when applying AI in learning analytics and assessment.

4. Methodology

In this section we present our novel models for skill prediction in detail, and introduce the design of our offline experiment to validate the models' performance and generalizability, in different scenarios of relevance to platforms and state departments of education. Section 4.1 describes the machine learning tools we will evaluate to address RQ1, and the results from the experiments mentioned in Section 4.2 will make our answers to RQ1. RQ2 will be answered by the results from the different analysis scenarios detailed in Section 4.2.2.

4.1. Models

The problem we are solving in this paper is: given any educational resource (e.g., problem, video, or skill from a source taxonomy), and a target skill taxonomy, predict the skill(s) that are associated with the resource. We use problems, videos, and skills collected from digital learning platforms as educational resources. They are all multimodal: problems have problem texts and associated images, videos have the video itself and text captions, and skills have skill descriptions and the problems that are linked to the skills (including problem texts and images) according to the source taxonomy. The target taxonomy for most experiments is the Common Core Mathematics Standards, where each skill has a paragraph of description. We also experimented with using taxonomies created by the digital learning platforms in our study as the target taxonomy. The detailed parameter setup can be found in Section 4.2.2.

We propose two models to tackle the problem, a classification model, and a similarity matching model. Fig. 2 shows the model architecture. The two models have a common feature encoder and fusion mechanism to combine multimodal data (e.g., problem text and an image), but then take different approaches to map the content encoding to predicted skill labels. Pseudocode of the algorithms can be found in Appendix B.

4.1.1. Feature encoder

The feature encoder consists of one encoder for each mode of input, and the output of each encoder is a real-valued vector. For example, for a problem with problem text and an image, a text encoder encodes the text into a text vector, and the image encoder encodes the image into an image vector. Similarly for a video with captions, we obtain a text vector for the captions and a video vector for the video. All feature encoders we use in this paper are publicly available pre-trained models from previous machine learning papers. Specifically, the text encoder is SentenceBERT¹⁵ (Reimers & Gurevych, 2019), the image encoder is EfficientNet-B7 (Tan & Le, 2019), and the video encoder is I3D (Carreira & Zisserman, 2017).

4.1.2. Fusion

After all input modes are represented as vectors, we leverage a fusion mechanism to merge them into a single vector to make it easier for the subsequent model components to utilize. The simplest way to accomplish this is to concatenate the vectors directly. But previous studies have shown that simple concatenation is generally inferior to more advanced fusion methods (Liu et al., 2018; Li et al., 2021). In our research, we therefore evaluate a fusion method called Multimodal Compact Bilinear Pooling (Fukui et al., 2016), which achieves higher performance than simple concatenation in all our experiments.

After a fused vector is obtained for each educational resource, the models will learn to map it to the ground truth skills. The two fused vectors in Fig. 2 are the same vector, we plot it this way solely for the convenience of visualization.

¹⁵ The paraphrase-mpnet-base-v2 version of SentenceBERT is used in this paper.

Fig. 2. An overview of the proposed models to map problems to skills. The models for videos have the same architecture, with the inputs being caption texts and videos instead. The point cloud beside each vector in the similarity matching model is the embedding space of the vector, each point represents one problem or one skill, and the colors represent skill labels. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

4.1.3. Missing images

Some problems do not have an associated image, and thus do not have the image vector. We propose to impute the missing image vectors based on the text vectors. Inspired by the centroid-based imputation method (Raja & Thangavel, 2020), we propose the following to impute the missing image vectors.

First, we find all existing image vectors, and run K-means clustering (Likas et al., 2003) on the vectors. Suppose we get k clusters, and the centroids of the k clusters are $c_1, \dots, c_k$. We train a neural network f that takes the corresponding text vector as input and outputs k weights $w_1, \dots, w_k$. We model the imputed image vector v as the weighted sum of the k centroids: $v = \sum_{i=1}^k w_i c_i$. The neural network f is trained on the mean squared error loss between the imputed image vector and the actual image vector. After training, we use the trained model to calculate the weights for the problems without images and construct the implicit image vectors with the weights.

The number of clusters k is 10 in our experiments, determined by the elbow method (Thorndike, 1953). The model f is a two-layer neural network. The hidden size is 512, and the activation function is ReLU (Nair & Hinton, 2010).

This approach achieves higher performance in all our experiments than simply filling the missing image vectors with the mean of all image vectors.

4.1.4. Classification

The classification model attempts to predict the exact set of skills associated with a resource. It maps the fused vector to the relevant skills by passing the vector through a fully connected neural network with binary cross entropy loss and outputting the probabilities of each skill label in the last layer. Since each OER can be associated with multiple skills, each skill has its own independent probability assigned to it, and the probability values for all skills together do not necessarily sum to 1. One weakness of the classification model is that it can only predict skills from taxonomies where we have observed ground truth labels in training.

We use a two-layer neural network with hidden size equal to the input size and ReLU activation in our experiments.

4.1.5. Similarity matching

The similarity matching model ranks skills in order of most likely match. It is not able to give a prediction of the exact set of skills associated with a resource, but it is able to match resources to a new skill taxonomy that it has never seen before. It extracts text vectors from target skill descriptions and learns an orthogonal matrix that transforms the content vectors onto the space of the skill description vectors, then measures the cosine similarity between the contents and skills. This method is borrowed from the machine translation field, where word vectors of one language are transformed onto the space of word vectors of another language via an orthogonal matrix (Smith et al., 2017).

To give a better intuition on the similarity matching model, we visualize the vector spaces for each vector in Fig. 2. The original vector spaces are high-dimensional, we reduce them to two dimensions using Principal Component Analysis (Abdi & Williams, 2010). All vectors are projected onto the two-dimensional plane formed by the first two principal components of the skill description vectors. Each point represents a skill (in the skill vector space) or a problem (in the problem vector spaces). The colors of vectors indicate different areas in Common Core. As seen from the graph, the orthogonal translation transforms the problem vectors to a similar shape as the skill text vectors. Note that orthogonal transformation, from the mathematical definition, is only applying rotations and reflections on the vectors, and does not change the scale or inner structure of the vector space.

4.2. Experiments

We conduct extensive experiments to evaluate the models. In this section we introduce the datasets we run experiments on, the design of the experiments, and the evaluation metrics we use.

Fig. 3 shows a framework to apply our proposed approach. In the data collection phase, we first collect OER content and the taxonomy that we want to map the content to. The OERs content can contain three types of media (text, images, and videos), and the taxonomy should consist of a list of skills and their descriptions. The next two steps are obtaining a sample of ground truth mappings between the OERs and the target taxonomy to train new models based on the obtained labels. If a pre-trained model is used, these two steps can be skipped. Next, is evaluation of the models. This can be accomplished with conventional train/test hold-out or cross validation approaches when training new models to evaluate label prediction accuracy. If the similarity matching method or the existing common core classification model is used, label prediction accuracy can be evaluated without hold-out or cross validation since no training is taking place. If the model's performance reaches the desired level (depending on the use case and requirements), the model can then be used in real-world applications. This framework applies to our experiment design and serves as a reference to researchers and practitioners interested in using these models.

4.2.1. Datasets

There are three data sources of our experiments. Two of them are OER platforms: Khan Academy¹⁶ and CK12,¹⁷ and their respective custom taxonomies. The US Common Core State Standards and its skill definitions is another data source. The subject areas of all data sources fall within K-12 mathematics.

From Khan Academy, we collected 21,475 problems, 7976 of which have at least one associated image, and 1140 videos with captions. The problem texts have 28 words per problem on average, and the video captions have 770 words per video. Khan Academy has its own skill taxonomy of 1049 skills. We also collected descriptions of those skills.

From CK12, we collected 19,996 problems, 3343 of which have at least one associated image. CK12 also has its own skill taxonomy. We collected the descriptions of the 373 CK12 skills that the problems are tagged with. We collected the Khan Academy and CK12 contents from the Kolibri project.¹⁸

The Common Core State Standards has a tree structure, where each skill is identified by the path from the root node to the skill's leaf node, and that path is encoded as the skill code. For example, "6.EE.A.1" is a skill code in the standards, where "6" stands for Grade 6, "EE" means it's an Expressions and Equations skill under Grade 6, "A" is a subdomain within "EE", and "1" is a subcategory within "A". The top level of a skill (e.g., "6") usually implies the grade level, with high school skills being an exception, where five top levels exist (i.e., "HAS", "HSF", "HSG", "HSN", and "HSS", meaning high school algebra, functions, geometry, number and quantity, and statistics and probability respectively). The second level (e.g., "EE") represents a specific area within the top level. The lower levels (e.g., "A" and "1") are subfields under the second level, and the codes are used only to distinguish the skills and have no semantic meanings, unlike the top two levels. Some skills have a finer granularity (e.g., "6.EE.A.2.A" has five levels) and some don't (e.g., "6.EE.A.1" has four levels). In this research, we take the top four levels for consistency, and any skills beyond that granularity are merged with the sibling skills. For example, "6.EE.A.2.A", "6.EE.A.2.B", and "6.EE.A.2.C" are combined into a single skill "6.EE.A.2". More details of the Common Core mathematics standards can be found on the official website¹⁹. At the time when the paper is written, there are 385 skills in Common Core math standards by our definition. We collected the descriptions of these skills.

Besides collecting each dataset, we were also able to get mappings between them. Specifically, both Khan Academy and CK12 provide the mappings from their skills to Common Core skills. The mappings can be both one-to-many and many-to-one. Since the problems and videos from Khan Academy and CK12 are linked to their own platform-specific taxonomies respectively, we can obtain the mappings from the problems and videos to the Common Core skills by assigning each problem or video the Common Core skills that are associated with the platform-specific skills that the problem or video is associated with. In this way, we mapped all problems and videos we collected to the Common Core skills, most of which (81% of Khan Academy problems and 65% of CK12 problems) have only one associated skill. In total, Khan Academy problems are linked to 329 Common Core skills, Khan Academy videos are linked to 143 Common Core skills, and CK12 problems are linked to 194 Common Core skills.

¹⁶ <https://www.khanacademy.org/>.

¹⁷ <https://www.ck12.org/>.

¹⁸ <https://learningequality.org/kolibri>.

¹⁹ <https://corestandards.org/>.

Fig. 3. An overview of the steps to apply the proposed approach. This framework guides our experiment designs and can be a reference for readers interested in applying these models.

4.2.2. Experiment setup

We conduct experiments for three tasks: the mapping from problems to skills, from videos to skills, and from skills to skills. Because we have two OER platforms and three taxonomies, we can simulate different real-world scenarios where new contents or new taxonomies are introduced.

For the problems to skills mapping task, we first train and cross-validate models with labels from Khan Academy problems to Common Core skills. In cross validation, the test problems are new problems in Khan Academy that are not seen in training, and the target taxonomy is the same as training (i.e., Common Core). We divide all Khan Academy problems to 10 folds, train the model 10 times, each time using one fold as test set and the other nine as training set, and take the average result of the 10 runs. This result represents a “new problems from the same platform to the same taxonomy” generalization level. In real-world applications, this corresponds to the use case where we have some problems labeled with one taxonomy at hand, and want to extend labeling other problems to the same taxonomy using what we have. We then test the models to map CK12 problems to Common Core skills, giving results for the “new problems from a new platform to the same taxonomy” generalization level, which represents a real-world application where we want to label problems from a new source leveraging what we know about an old content source. These two levels are supported by both the classification model and similarity matching model. The similarity matching model can go one step further to map items to a completely new taxonomy not seen in training, thanks to the unified embeddings we use in the feature encoder. All content vectors, regardless of the source, should theoretically be in the same space, and all skill vectors, regardless of the taxonomy, should be in the same space too, therefore we can use the trained similarity matching model to directly map new contents to new skills. The easiest scenario in this generalization is “the same problems from the same platform to a new taxonomy”, which is practically useful when we want to map existing contents to a newly introduced taxonomy. A slightly harder one is the “new problems from the same platform to a new taxonomy” level. The two levels above are trained on Khan Academy problems to Khan Academy skills and tested on Khan Academy to Common Core skills. The hardest generalization is “new problems from a new platform to a new taxonomy”, which is of interest if readers use our open-sourced Common Core skill tagging models trained on Khan Academy to label any arbitrary items to any arbitrary taxonomy. This generalization level is tested by applying the model trained on labels from Khan Academy problems to Common Core skills to the mapping of CK12 problems to CK12 skills. All the “new taxonomy” generalizations are zero-shot learning as we haven’t seen any test classes at training time. The classification model, however, does not have this level of generalization because the target classes are defined and fixed at the training time.

For the videos to skills mapping task, since we only have videos collected from Khan Academy, we only evaluate models on Khan Academy videos labeled with Common Core skills. This represents the “new videos from the same platform to the same taxonomy” level of generalization.

For the skills to skills mapping task, because we have the mappings between all three taxonomies, Khan Academy, CK12, and Common Core, we can test both the “new skills from the same platform to the same taxonomy” level and the “new skills from a new platform to the same taxonomy” level. The former is achieved by training and cross-validating models on the labels from Khan Academy skills to Common Core skills, and the latter is done by applying the models to map CK12 skills to Common Core skills. Because all Khan Academy skills and CK12 skills have problems associated within the platform, we use these problems as inputs for the skills as well, when building the feature vectors. Therefore, the input modes for skills to skills mapping also have both texts and images, similar to problems to skills mapping.

We run all the experiments with different input modes (e.g., text only, image only, text and image) to understand how input modes affect the results.

In real-world applications, sometimes we may already know the grade level or the grade range level (e.g., kindergarten, elementary school, middle school, high school) of a given problem, video, or skill, and only need to map the content to a skill within that grade or grade range. To give an updated expectation of accuracy in those cases, we also evaluate the models with a grade filter and a grade range filter on the target skills to reduce the number of skills considered for a given educational resource and report the results respectively.

4.2.3. Evaluation metrics

To get a holistic view of the models’ performance, we evaluate them with a set of metrics: precision, recall, mean reciprocal rank (MRR), and accuracy (if applicable). Resources are linked to at most 3 skills, so we report Recall@3, which represents the percentage of the true labels captured in the top 3 results, to ensure that the best possible result could be 1. But most of them have only one associated

Fig. 4. A summary of problems to skills mapping results using Recall@3. All models are using text + image data.

skill, therefore we additionally report Precision@1, which captures the percentage of the time at least one of the true labels made it into the top result. Recall@3 is sensitive to multi-skill case because more true labels mean the top 3 results are less likely to cover all true labels, while Precision@1 is sensitive to multi-skill case in the opposite direction, since more true labels means the top result is more likely to hit one of the true labels. Therefore, we also introduce mean reciprocal rank to alleviate the shortcomings. MRR is calculated by averaging the reciprocals of the first correct prediction's rank for each problem ($MRR = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{r_i}$, where r_i is the rank of the first correct prediction for problem i). MRR is less sensitive to the number of true skills per problem, as it's just looking at the first relevant prediction. The classification model will output an independent probability for each skill, so we can use a threshold (0.5 in our experiments) to predict the exact set of skills per problem, thus we report accuracy for the classification model. A prediction is accurate only when the set of predicted skills is identical to the ground truth. The similarity matching model, on the other hand, does not have a reliable way to predict the exact set of skills, so we do not report accuracy with that model.

5. Results

In this section we present the experiment results. As we discussed earlier, there are three different experiment tasks: Section 5.1 is the problems to skills mapping, Section 5.2 is the videos to skills mapping, and Section 5.3 is the mapping of skills in one taxonomy to skills in another taxonomy.

Depending on the use cases, the results have different real-world implications. If a mislabeled skill is to be used in an intelligent tutor, it will likely lead to over or under practice (e.g., if a student is practicing a skill by working through relevant problems, under practice may occur if a set of items that should be tagged to an easier skill are mis-mapped to the current skill). While remote, a positive possibility is that it helps students make connections to related skills, since the models are not likely making random errors, but instead making an error involving some degree of overlapping semantics with the true skill. In the OER scenario of a teacher choosing items based on a skill, "false negatives" (a label should be predicted but is not) could leave the teacher less problems to choose from and add more burdens to the teacher, while "false positives" (a wrong label is predicted) could lead to student confusion that slows subject mastery. Typically, though not always, higher recall means fewer false negatives; higher precision means fewer false positives; and higher MRR and accuracy imply fewer occurrences in both false negatives and false positives.

5.1. Problems to skills mapping

The results reflect five levels of generalization depending on whether the source content pool is new and whether the target taxonomy is new at inference time. The five levels are: new problems from the same platform to the same taxonomy, new problems from a new platform to the same taxonomy, the same problems from the same platform to a new taxonomy, new problems from the same platform to a new taxonomy, and new problems from a new platform to a new taxonomy. A summary of the five generalization levels is shown in Fig. 4, and detailed experiment results can be found in Appendix A.

From Fig. 4 we see that the Recall@3 drops a lot when generalizing to an unseen platform. A previous study (Patikorn et al., 2019) has similar findings too. There could be several reasons for this. A new platform probably means a new style of problems (e.g., one has mainly word problems for a skill, while the other prefers more abstract equations). Also, the distributions of skills in two platforms are different. For instance, in CK12 we have 379 problems (1.9% out of all CK12 problems) for the skill "7.SP.B.4", but in Khan Academy there are only 15 problems (0.07% out of all Khan Academy problems) for this skill. When training on Khan Academy, we probably do not have sufficient information from the 15 problems to learn a good model for this skill, and when evaluating on CK12, the weakness of the model is amplified because we use it to predict skills for a lot more problems.

Another observation is that the classification model is usually better than the similarity matching model, but it does not work for new taxonomy generalizations. This implies that there is a trade-off between the two models. Therefore, in Section 7 we provide detailed guidance on which model to use based on the use cases.

From Appendix A we can also see that text is more effective than images in skill tagging in all scenarios, but combining texts and images marginally improves the model performance.

Overall, the results demonstrate that our models are effective for the skill tagging task. For the simplest scenario "new problems

Table 1

Khan Academy videos to Common Core skills mapping results. The results are cross validated at the Khan Academy video level.

Filter	Mode(s)	Classification Model				Similarity Matching Model		
		Precision@1	Recall@3	MRR	Accuracy	Precision@1	Recall@3	MRR
No Filter	Caption	0.925	0.928	0.946	0.867	0.603	0.627	0.688
	Video	0.874	0.875	0.892	0.837	0.076	0.129	0.160
	Caption + Video	0.931	0.930	0.951	0.869	0.678	0.681	0.745
Grade Range Filter	Caption	0.954	0.976	0.968	0.897	0.761	0.839	0.829
	Video	0.894	0.928	0.916	0.854	0.367	0.476	0.476
	Caption + Video	0.952	0.976	0.967	0.894	0.802	0.861	0.857
Grade Filter	Caption	0.975	0.994	0.985	0.925	0.867	0.935	0.918
	Video	0.926	0.969	0.952	0.876	0.441	0.689	0.619
	Caption + Video	0.976	0.994	0.985	0.920	0.885	0.942	0.928

from the same platform to the same taxonomy”, the best MRR is 0.552 for no filter, 0.642 for grade range filter, and 0.74 for grade filter. Considering that an MRR above 0.5 means the average rank of the first relevant skill is between the first and the second places, this result shows that the model is pretty good at predicting the correct skill labels. The performance of the hardest generalization “new problems from a new platform to a new taxonomy” is lower than other generalization levels, but still not randomly bad. For instance, we get an MRR of 0.317 with grade filter in text-only mode, which means that on average the correct skill label appears between the third and fourth predictions. Given that there are 24 skills per grade on average, we believe that the model does produce outputs in the right direction that could potentially be leveraged to help with the manual labeling process.

5.2. Videos to skills mapping

Since we only have video data for Khan Academy, we can only get the results for the “new videos from the same platform to the same taxonomy” generalization level. We evaluate the models with cross-validation within Khan Academy and show the results in Table 1. The key findings are:

- The performance is better than problems. Considering that the ground-truth labels are produced by human experts, the high accuracy (above 0.85 for all skill filters) indicates that the models achieve a near expert level.
- The classification model is better than the similarity matching model, consistent with the findings on problems.
- Combining modes does not bring a performance gain.

5.3. Skills to skills mapping

Since we have three taxonomies (Khan Academy, CK12, and Common Core), we can test two generalization levels: “new skills from the same platform to the same taxonomy”, and “new skills from a new platform to the same taxonomy”. The target taxonomy remains the same, i.e., Common Core.

5.3.1. New skills from the same platform to the same taxonomy

Table 2 is the 10-fold cross-validated mapping results of Khan Academy skills to Common Core skills. Combining text and image improves the performance moderately. Classification models are better than similarity matching models with no filter, but worse with grade range filter and grade filter.

In this experiment, 1049 source skills are mapped to 329 target skills. We use 10-fold cross-validation, so 90% of target skills are used in training and 10% are held out for testing.

5.3.2. New skills from a new platform to the same taxonomy

Table 3 shows the mapping results from CK12 skills to Common Core skills, with the models trained on Khan Academy skills to Common Core skills. Similarity matching models perform better than classification models in all cases. While the performance is expectedly worse than skills from the same platform, it’s still much better than a random model. Especially, the MRR for no filter condition is above 0.5, which means on average the first correct skill will appear in the first two predictions. If we know the grade level of a problem, the MRR would even reach 0.7.

6. Analysis

To better understand the models and their performance, we conducted three additional model and data analyses.

6.1. Analysis of the limited utility of images

One observation from our experiments is that multimodal inputs do not provide much performance gain compared to text-only

Table 2

Khan Academy skills to Common Core skills mapping results. The results are cross validated at the skill hold-out level.

Filter	Mode(s)	Classification Model				Similarity Matching Model		
		Precision@1	Recall@3	MRR	Accuracy	Precision@1	Recall@3	MRR
No Filter	Text	0.613	0.756	0.722	0.334	0.605	0.655	0.717
	Image	0.217	0.334	0.327	0.034	0.187	0.225	0.271
	Text + Image	0.633	0.774	0.738	0.393	0.609	0.667	0.727
Grade Range Filter	Text	0.632	0.808	0.753	0.390	0.673	0.837	0.784
	Image	0.323	0.508	0.471	0.116	0.244	0.408	0.383
	Text + Image	0.631	0.835	0.740	0.410	0.693	0.851	0.797
Grade Filter	Text	0.737	0.888	0.830	0.444	0.754	0.925	0.851
	Image	0.424	0.648	0.586	0.177	0.375	0.571	0.532
	Text + Image	0.742	0.904	0.836	0.475	0.787	0.926	0.869

Table 3
CK12 skills to Common Core skills mapping results. The models are trained on Khan Academy skills to Common Core skills mapping.

Filter	Mode(s)	Classification Model				Similarity Matching Model		
		Precision@1	Recall@3	MRR	Accuracy	Precision@1	Recall@3	MRR
No Filter	Text	0.304	0.345	0.434	0.074	0.369	0.464	0.516
	Image	0.094	0.114	0.172	0.006	0.059	0.090	0.130
	Text + Image	0.339	0.386	0.461	0.083	0.404	0.476	0.550
Grade Range Filter	Text	0.405	0.528	0.544	0.113	0.519	0.595	0.641
	Image	0.117	0.173	0.219	0.029	0.066	0.120	0.165
	Text + Image	0.423	0.524	0.557	0.121	0.498	0.598	0.637
Grade Filter	Text	0.456	0.647	0.616	0.104	0.573	0.700	0.705
	Image	0.204	0.334	0.356	0.033	0.134	0.280	0.299
	Text + Image	0.501	0.631	0.639	0.110	0.568	0.708	0.702

inputs (only 4% improvement on average). We believe that multiple reasons led to the results. First, images alone are much less accurate for skill tagging than text alone, but good performance from both modes is typically needed to produce a better combined model. To compare images and texts, we calculated silhouette scores (Rousseeuw, 1987) to measure how the vectors fit with its ground truth skill labels. Silhouette score is a value between -1 and 1 , where higher score indicates better clustering. Using the ground truth skill labels as the clustering labels, and cosine distance as the distance metric, the silhouette score is -0.22 for image vectors and 0.03 for text vectors. Intuitively this suggests that image vectors with different skill labels have more overlap with each other compared to text vectors, which makes it harder to find the correct labels for images. To better visualize that, we plot the image vectors in Fig. 5. The vectors are reduced to 2 dimensions using t-SNE (Van der Maaten & Hinton, 2008), and the color indicates the second level of the ground truth Common Core skill labels. As seen from the left figure, there's much overlap between images of different labels. As we zoom into one region specifically, we see that while the images all look similar (containing a triangle), their skill labels are different. In these cases, the text of the problem must be consulted to disambiguate the skill associated with the problem.

Another reason why multimodal input is not very helpful is that there are many problems that do not have images. Only 37% of problems in Khan Academy and 17% in CK12 have images. Although we reconstruct the implicit image vectors for those without images from the text vectors, that can only alleviate the problem to a certain extent.

Furthermore, the quality of the image embeddings may also be an important factor. The image encoder EfficientNet-B7 is trained on the ImageNet dataset (Deng et al., 2009, pp. 248–255), which is a general classification dataset with 1000 labels. However, the images in math problems are very domain specific. The pre-trained model may not be able to capture the nuances in our datasets.

Despite these weaknesses, we do observe moderate improvements using images for within-platform labeling.

6.2. Skill tagging error analysis

We also want to know how our two models behave across the skill labels, and in particular how bad the predictions were when they were wrong. We visualize the confusion matrix with a heatmap for the top level (Fig. 6) and the second level (Fig. 7) of skill labels. Each grid in the heatmaps represents the percentage of the problems with the ground truth label (x-axis) that are predicted as the y-axis label. From Fig. 6 we see that when the models make mistakes, they are more likely to predict a skill of a grade level that is closer to the ground truth grade level than one that is farther. This makes sense because skills from closer grades may have more commonalities and are thus harder to distinguish. We also see that the models perform worse in the primary grade range compared to other grades, especially for the similarity matching model.

From Fig. 7, we see that the models completely mislabel some second levels, like IC (Making Inferences & Justifying Conclusions), MG (Modeling with Geometry), and Q (Quantities). These are all high school skills, and the models mistake them for some lower-grade skills that are from a similar area. For example, the model predicts most IC skills as SP (Statistics & Probabilities) and most MG skills as G (Geometry), both SP and G are second levels for lower-grade skills. In our datasets, the IC problems and SP problems often contain the same set of words that are closely related to statistics but are less frequent in other areas of skills, such as population, mean, data, probability, etc. The same applies to MG and G. That could explain why the models are not able to distinguish between them.

6.3. Data sensitivity analysis

How much training data is necessary to obtain good results? This may correspond to how much work manual labelers must do until our proposed machine learning approaches can begin to be helpful. We specifically analyze the amount of labeled data that is needed by the similarity matching and classification models with different levels of filtering evaluated with Recall@3. For this experiment, we began with a minimum of 25 labeled Khan Academy problems with images for the similarity matching model. Since there are 329 total skills, this minimum number of problems represents an example of zero-shot learning, where many skills (or classes) are predicted in the test set that were never seen in the training data. The data sensitivity analysis for the classification model starts with 329 samples, one labeled problem per unique skill, since it requires that a class be observed in training to be predicted in the test set. In Fig. 8 we can see Recall@3 rising steadily from 25 samples up until 5000 samples, where performance largely asymptotes up through the full size of the training set (19,325). The classification model exhibits similar performance, except that the no filter classification model climbs in Recall@3 more steeply than the rest, nearly reaching the performance of the similarity matching model with grade range filter at 5000

samples. Considering that the ground truth labels were produced by domain experts, both models can reach near expert level (Recall@3 of 0.8) with 5000 training samples and grade filter.

Non-expert human labeling performance for this task has been measured around a Recall@3 of 0.5 for the same taxonomy (i.e., Common Core) with CK12 problems and with grade filter enabled (Ren et al., 2024). That is, labelers were only given the skill options appropriate to the grade level of the problem. This means that as few as 100 labeled problems are needed for the model to achieve this human level of performance using the similarity matching with grade filter model.

7. Policy recommendations for implementation

We release our pre-trained models that map educational resources to Common Core standards, and also release the source code to train new models. Depending on the use case, we offer different recommendations on how state departments of education, OER platforms, and other practitioners might utilize these models given our findings. These recommendations represent our conclusions to RQ2: which alignment models may be of practical use in different scenarios.

When using our pre-trained models, we offer the following guidance:

- If your target taxonomy is Common Core and
 - If the content you are tagging is from Khan Academy: prefer the classification model and expect to have results similar to Appendix Table A-1 for problems, Table 1 for videos, and Table 2 for skills. The models have a decent performance and may be applied with a few human modifications.
 - If the content you are tagging is not from Khan Academy: prefer the classification model for problems and expect Appendix Table A-2, and the similarity matching model for skills and expect Table 3. The models are not bad but require manual updates to the mappings produced before use.
- If your target taxonomy is not Common Core: use the similarity matching model only and expect to have results similar to Appendix Table A-5. Model application to this scenario of *new problems from new platform to new taxonomy* is viable for real-world use, but only if filters can be used to narrow the scope of the matches to the new taxonomy, for example using a grade-level filter. Additionally, the predictions of our model in this scenario should be used in collaboration with a human coder, as a recommendation or initial alignment that can then be modified by a person.

When training models from scratch, we offer the following guidance:

- If the taxonomy of the test set is the same as training and
 - If the content you are tagging is from the same platform as the training set: the classification model is usually better and expect to have results similar to Appendix Table A-1 for problems, Table 1 for videos, and Table 2 for skills; furthermore, if you have a limited number of labels to train on, use Fig. 8 as an estimate on the accuracy at your training size. The models have a decent performance and may be applied with a few human modifications.
 - If the content you are tagging is from a different platform than the training set: no model is always better than the other and expect Appendix Table A-2 for problems and Table 3 for skills. The models are not bad but may require manual updates to the mappings produced before use.
 - If you plan to use your models on a different taxonomy than training, use similarity matching model only and
 - If the content you are tagging is the same as training, expect Appendix Table A3. The models are not bad but may require manual updates to the mappings produced before use.
 - If the content you are tagging comes from the same platform as training, expect Appendix Table A4. The models are not bad but may require manual updates to the mappings produced before use.
 - If the content you are tagging comes from a different platform, expect Appendix Table A5. Note that the models can only produce results as initial alignment or recommendations that require human modifications.
-

Note, that only when the content source and target taxonomy are both the same as training will the models' performance be possible to reach near-expert level. When either or both source and target change, the accuracy will drop. This is in line with previous findings by Patikorn et al. (2019).

8. Discussion

8.1. How effective are AI models in skill tagging? (RQ1)

For labeling the skill of educational videos, we found AI models to be very effective. Without knowledge of the grade-level of the video, the best model scored an accuracy of 0.869 and scored 0.925 with knowledge of the grade-level. The transcript of the video provided the essential information needed for the training of the models, with the addition of video frames being negligible, resulting in a plus or minus 0.002 difference. There were 143 total Common Core skill labels for the videos with an average of seven videos per label used for training. At this level of performance, the models could be applied to labeling of video OERs without human supervision.

Problem labeling saw much-reduced performance compared to video labeling, with no model performing at the level necessary for full automation (i.e., no human supervision), with the highest accuracy model registering an accuracy of 0.346. However, at this level, where the grade-level of the problem is known and at least 15 problems were trained on for each unique label, performance is at the level where AI models have been shown beneficial for use in collaboration with human expert labelers (e.g., an accuracy of 0.44 by Desmond et al., 2021). There were 329 total Common Core skill labels for Khan Academy problems. With 15 problems per label and 329 labels, this equates to approximately 5000 data points, an inflection point for training data in Fig. 8's data sensitivity analysis. Interestingly, this is more data points per label than the video labeling task but with less than half the accuracy – video labeling is 2.6x more accurate. The videos, however, have around 26x more words in their transcripts than the problems have in their problem text. Our findings therefore suggest that it is more valuable for these models to have more text to train on than more examples. For labeling problems to new taxonomies, AI performance levels where they could be viable in human-in-the-loop scenarios can be obtained by training 15 problems per label from the new taxonomy before making predictions of the rest, or by using the similarity matching algorithm to make predictions of a new taxonomy with no existing labels. The latter approach scored a Recall@3 of 0.671, making it a

Fig. 5. Visualization of dimensionality reduced image vectors from all Khan Academy problems in our dataset, with four highlighted problems shown. The displayed problems are from four different skills but have very similar images and vector locations in the lower dimensional space, exemplifying why images do not always contribute to greater label prediction accuracy.

Fig. 6. Confusion heatmap of skill predictions according to the top-level common core skill categorization. Each cell in the heatmap represents the percentage of the problems with the ground truth label (x-axis) that are predicted as the y-axis label.

Fig. 7. Confusion heatmap of skill predictions according to the second-level common core skill categorization. Each grid in the heatmap represents the percentage of the problems with the ground truth label (x-axis) that are predicted as the y-axis label.

borderline approach in terms of what is viable for human-in-the-loop recommendation.

Mapping one taxonomy to another performed in between video and problem labeling, with the best model achieving a 0.475 accuracy using the classification model and a best Recall@3 of 0.926 using the similarity matching algorithm. Both scores are within the bounds of usefulness for AI models to be used in a human-in-the-loop, or human expert supervised scenario.

8.2. Which models are of practical use in different scenarios? (RQ2)

In this section, we will give a few examples that mirror motivating examples from the introduction and describe the viability of the introduced models, given our results, in those scenarios. When an OERs platform is introduced, the platform would need to tag its OERs with skills from one or more taxonomies to make them searchable and more likely to be seen and utilized. Such a platform could make use of our models that map new problems or videos from a new platform to an existing taxonomy or manually label a subset of their

Fig. 8. Recall@3 at the “new problems within the same platform to the same taxonomy” generalization level with different training data sizes. Models are trained and cross-validated on labels from Khan Academy problems to Common Core skills.

OERs with a new taxonomy and then train our classification model. To achieve a performance level necessary to likely improve expert labeling with human-in-the-loop supervision, 15 problems per new taxonomy label would need to be manually tagged, or seven in the case of videos due to their lengthy transcripts. To achieve a level equivalent to novice skill taggers, only a total of 100 problems would need to be tagged in total, covering only a subset of the taxonomy’s skills.

Another use case is for the update of standards. Departments of education at various governmental levels may update the standards to improve the utility of the taxonomy, as do most educational technology platforms or alternative taxonomies may be introduced by other countries or private curricula that OER platforms may want to appeal to. In this circumstance, the OERs are unchanged, but need to be mapped to a new or modified taxonomy, where our models that map existing OERs on existing platforms to a new taxonomy are applicable. From Section 7 we see that the models can provide mapping results (Recall@3 of 0.671) that are above novice labeler performance (i.e., Recall@3 > 0.50) but borderline performance with respect to improving expert labeling with human-in-the-loop supervision (i.e., short of Recall@3 of 0.80). For this scenario, the platform would however already need to have trained a competent model on their own OERs and the previous taxonomy labels. Fifteen examples per label is recommended for that training set. No labeling examples from the new taxonomy are needed.

8.3. Implications

Our models have some pedagogical and research implications. Teachers have their own teaching style and even standards, the standards mapping techniques introduced in this paper can make it easier for teachers to adapt their standards to a common standard and vice versa. For researchers, the paper sets a new baseline for mapping OERs to US Common Core and mapping OERs to a new taxonomy. Future work can further develop these and future machine learning models and evaluate and compare them to our baseline.

Our classification models also have implications for the era of Generative AI that has already begun (Lim et al., 2023). Research is already being conducted on generating problems (Bhandari et al., 2023) and hints (Pardos & Bhandari, 2023) using large language models, with industry likely following suit. This could lead to an explosion in AI-generated content. If this new content were to be considered OERs on the same platform (perhaps using a language model fine-tuned on the platform’s existing OERs) with a desired tagging from an existing taxonomy, our best performing model could be used in this case (Recall@3 of 0.813), which could save content author time by allowing them to select among a list of three recommended skills.

Our findings could have implications for computer adaptive tutoring systems as well. Such systems often have their own internal skill models (Aleven & Koedinger, 2013; Razzaq et al., 2007). This can make it prohibitive to adopt external content into these systems. By using our models to tag problem and video content external to an adaptive tutoring system with the taxonomy of that system, computer tutors could include OERs as part of their problem pools instead of relying solely on much more expensive in-house content production.

Finally, the nimbler re-alignment and prospects for subsequent lower human workload burden that these models afford could open possibilities for iterative development of state standards at a more frequent cadence than has been implemented in the past (see Fig. 1). Institutional K-12 education still followed an academic year cohort model and teachers must prepare their curricular materials for the upcoming academic year. This places a limit on standards being updated mid-year; however, with the proliferation of digital educational assessment and tutoring systems, data is streaming in that can help curriculum and standards designers improve their taxonomies with updates that could occur every few years and come with a digest of changes communicable to educators. With machine learning-based skill labeling, re-aligning existing digital curricular materials to the iterated taxonomy would not be prohibitively burdensome.

9. Limitations and future work

One limitation of this work is that we only focused on the mathematics skills of the Common Core State Standards. Future work is needed to evaluate the effectiveness of the models on other fields (e.g., English language arts), other standards (e.g., Next Generation Science Standards), and potentially standards in other languages (e.g., Chinese National Curriculum Standards).

Moreover, how LLMs like ChatGPT perform in the skill tagging task is an interesting prospect. GPT models may be able to perform this task more accurately moving forward, but are likely to still require validated human inputs to learn from, either as in-context training data, or training data for fine-tuning. An important area of future research includes comparing the performance of GPT models under different training and prompting regimes to better understand how they might perform on the tasks we present in this paper. The application of GPT-4 to this task is a very promising endeavor as its multimodal capabilities improve.

Another future research area is how the models can better assist humans in real-world applications. As we discussed earlier, the models' problem labeling performance is not good enough for full automation without human supervision but should be accurate enough to provide valuable inputs for human labelers. How will people view and act on these inputs? How can we design ways to make the best of the models' predictions for human review? Answering these questions can help us better understand the value of the algorithm and maximize its real-world utility.

10. Conclusion

In this paper, we proposed new models for mapping educational resources to skill taxonomies. This work is the first to incorporate multimodal data in these models and established a benchmark in skill tagging of problems, videos, and skills to the Common Core State Standards. It also evaluates recent advances of machine learning tools on the novel task of skill tagging problems to an out-of-sample taxonomy, not seen in training. To answer RQ1: how effective are machine learning models in automatically updating OER classification to reflect a new taxonomy, we revealed that the application of zero-shot learning can be used to align OERs to a newly introduced taxonomy, providing initial tagging of content before any manual tagging has been done. The accuracy of this type of skill tagging absent any examples is relatively low, however it has been shown to be of sufficient utility when assisting in the manual alignment process to increase human coder speed and accuracy (Desmond et al., 2021). We found that images contribute only a small amount to alignment accuracy, but that this small contribution was only realized by using fusion techniques which intelligently merge multimodal representations together. We anticipate that the contribution of fusion to model accuracy will increase as AI image embeddings continue to improve and allow for more nuanced differences in images to be distinguished. We also found video labeling to be of a sufficiently high performance level for this method to be used without human supervision and concluded that this task performed considerably better than problem labeling due to video transcripts containing substantially more words (~26x) than problem text. Lastly, we confirmed prior findings that using large language models (e.g., SentenceBERT) for representing the text of OERs is particularly useful in this task and expect accuracy to continue improving commensurate with advances in language model-based embeddings.

We found that completely automatic re-labeling of existing and new content is not viable when a new taxonomy is introduced, but our tools make the realignment process much more tractable by requiring only a few labels and automating the rest. Non-expert, human level labeling performance can be achieved with only 100 labeled problems. Furthermore, the model can label problems with skills not seen in the 100 examples. Near maximum performance is achieved with 5000 labeled problems, far short of the total available training data. This performance can be achieved using off-the-shelf open licensed pre-trained language embedding models (i.e., SentenceBERT), a pre-trained image vectorizer (i.e., EfficientNet), and a predefined fusion model to combine text and image representations (i.e., Multimodal Compact Bilinear Pooling).

When a new taxonomy is introduced or a platform endeavors to adopt an existing taxonomy, the benefits of our introduced methodology over manual tagging are considerable. For a platform with 21,000 problems, for example, like our Khan Academy dataset, only 0.40% need be tagged to get non-expert, human level performance on the remaining 99.60% of problems. Fewer than a quarter of the problems need to be tagged to get maximum labeling performance on the remaining 75%. Even when no sample of problems are tagged to the new taxonomy, performance of the model is likely still viable for real-world use when grade filters are present, and the skill predictions serve as suggestions to human coders.

With a minimum manual labeling work savings of 75% and maximum of 99%, we believe the models introduced have significant implications for education technology providers and education policy. As our answer to RQ2: which models may be of practical use in different scenarios, we provided recommendations on which models are effective in which real-world scenarios and how to use them. The implementation of these and better models, as AI technology improves, will substantially alleviate the burden of re-alignment, and potentially reduce pressure on standards policy makers to continue to iterate and evolve curricula and associated taxonomies.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Zhi Li: Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Visualization.
Zachary A. Pardos: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Resources, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.
Cheng Ren: Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization.

Data availability

Code, Common Core embeddings, and example problems with problem text can be found in our public code repository.

Acronyms

OER	Open Educational Resources
LLM	Large Language Models
BERT	Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
AIEd	Artificial Intelligence in Education
CCSS	Common Core State Standards
MRR	Mean Reciprocal Rank

Appendix

A. Problems to Skills Mapping Results

Appendix Table A-1

Khan Academy problems to Common Core skills mapping results. The results are cross-validated at the Khan Academy problem level²⁰

Filter	Mode(s)	Classification Model				Similarity Matching Model		
		Precision@1	Recall@3	MRR	Accuracy	Precision@1	Recall@3	MRR
No Filter	Text	0.427	0.558	0.538	0.196	0.315	0.378	0.439
	Image	0.167	0.242	0.256	0.045	0.116	0.140	0.184
	Text + Image	0.441	0.574	0.552	0.223	0.341	0.407	0.467
Grade Range Filter	Text	0.471	0.704	0.620	0.250	0.384	0.602	0.548
	Image	0.271	0.435	0.408	0.116	0.158	0.263	0.285
	Text + Image	0.504	0.716	0.642	0.270	0.442	0.638	0.592
Grade Filter	Text	0.610	0.800	0.734	0.340	0.555	0.788	0.704
	Image	0.371	0.566	0.530	0.139	0.274	0.461	0.445
	Text + Image	0.618	0.812	0.740	0.346	0.587	0.805	0.726

Appendix Table A-2

CK12 problems to Common Core skills mapping results. The models are trained on Khan Academy problems to Common Core skills mapping

Filter	Mode(s)	Classification Model				Similarity Matching Model		
		Precision@1	Recall@3	MRR	Accuracy	Precision@1	Recall@3	MRR
No Filter	Text	0.182	0.211	0.290	0.040	0.152	0.186	0.253
	Image	0.043	0.067	0.115	0.001	0.066	0.070	0.117
	Text + Image	0.175	0.207	0.286	0.041	0.172	0.206	0.279
Grade Range Filter	Text	0.229	0.329	0.365	0.058	0.230	0.312	0.360
	Image	0.073	0.123	0.174	0.010	0.072	0.100	0.156
	Text + Image	0.231	0.325	0.367	0.059	0.231	0.317	0.367
Grade Filter	Text	0.318	0.458	0.476	0.067	0.313	0.478	0.481
	Image	0.145	0.269	0.304	0.025	0.127	0.249	0.281
	Text + Image	0.322	0.465	0.477	0.061	0.314	0.480	0.483

Appendix Table A-3

Khan Academy problems to Common Core skills mapping results. The models are trained on the same set of Khan Academy problems but mapped to Khan Academy skills

Filter	Mode(s)	Similarity Matching Model		
		Precision@1	Recall@3	MRR
No Filter	Text	0.182	0.270	0.300
	Image	0.056	0.094	0.117
	Text + Image	0.225	0.323	0.350
Grade Range Filter	Text	0.283	0.428	0.430
	Image	0.094	0.191	0.208
	Text + Image	0.333	0.484	0.479

(continued on next page)

²⁰ We've tested with fitting a similarity threshold from the training set to predict the exact set of labels for the similarity matching model, but it does not produce good enough results, (e.g., 0.06 accuracy with no-filter and text + image case), so we do not include those results in this paper.

Appendix Table A-3 (continued)

Filter	Mode(s)	Similarity Matching Model		
		Precision@1	Recall@3	MRR
Grade Filter	Text	0.392	0.632	0.570
	Image	0.180	0.342	0.342
	Text + Image	0.442	0.671	0.610

Appendix Table A-4

Khan Academy problems to Common Core skills mapping results. The models are trained on a different set of Khan Academy problems to Khan Academy skills mapping

Filter	Mode(s)	Similarity Matching Model		
		Precision@1	Recall@3	MRR
No Filter	Text	0.141	0.236	0.259
	Image	0.035	0.075	0.093
	Text + Image	0.168	0.265	0.289
Grade Range Filter	Text	0.240	0.390	0.391
	Image	0.072	0.154	0.180
	Text + Image	0.263	0.411	0.413
Grade Filter	Text	0.361	0.599	0.541
	Image	0.152	0.311	0.315
	Text + Image	0.389	0.620	0.564

Appendix Table A-5

CK12 problems to CK12 skills mapping results. The models are trained on Khan Academy problems to Common Core skills mapping

Filter	Mode(s)	Similarity Matching Model		
		Precision@1	Recall@3	MRR
No Filter	Text	0.058	0.137	0.137
	Image	0.008	0.025	0.035
	Text + Image	0.059	0.142	0.139
Grade Range Filter	Text	0.090	0.209	0.194
	Image	0.012	0.040	0.057
	Text + Image	0.091	0.209	0.195
Grade Filter	Text	0.176	0.362	0.317
	Image	0.039	0.126	0.136
	Text + Image	0.163	0.346	0.305

B. Algorithms

Here is the pseudo-code for training and testing the classification and similarity matching models. The two models share the feature extraction part.

```

For training:
Initialize classification network C. Initialize translation matrix T.
for problem, label in training_problems, training_labels:
    text_vector = SentenceBERT.encode(problem.text)
    image_vector = EfficientNet.encode(problem.image)
    vector = MultimodalCompactBilinearPooling.fusion(text_vector, image_vector)

    // Classification model
    loss = BinaryCrossEntropyLoss(vector, label)
    update C to minimize loss

    // Similarity matching model
    skill_vector = SentenceBERT.encode(label)
    translated_vector = vector * T
    cosine_similarity = cosine_similarity(skill_vector, translated_vector)
    update T to maximize cosine_similarity

For testing:
for problem in testing_problems:
    text_vector = SentenceBERT.encode(problem.text)
    image_vector = EfficientNet.encode(problem.image)
    vector = MultimodalCompactBilinearPooling.fusion(text_vector, image_vector)

    // Classification model
    probabilities = C.predict(vector)
    predicted_labels = where(probabilities > threshold)

    // Similarity matching model
    translated_vector = vector * T
    skill_vectors = SentenceBERT.encode(all_labels)
    cosine_similarity = cosine_similarity(translated_vector, skill_vectors)
    label_ranks = argsort(cosine_similarity, reverse=True)

```

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